

THE CONTRIBUTION OF VOLUNTARY, FAITH BASED AND NON GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS TO SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN TURKANA COUNTY, KENYA 1986-2006

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Abstract:

The voluntary, religious and Non-Governmental Organizations have done tremendous work in Kenya in the areas of socio-economic development. It is indicated in this study that these organizations especially Voluntary organizations set foot in Kenya in an attempt to mitigate the suffering of refugees from war torn African countries hosted by Kenya at the Kakuma Refugee Camp located in Turkana County. That is when they discovered that even the local populations were adversely affected by challenges of drought, famine, illiteracy, conflict, cattle rustling and diseases. The study exposes how church organizations, voluntary agencies and NGOs contributed to the socioeconomic development of Turkana County residents in areas of medical, conflict resolution, education and provision of social amenities from 1986 to 2006. This study obtained data from both primary and secondary sources. Interviews were conducted after a purposive sampling. This was preferred so as to target respondents who are NGO officials, government officers and employees of other specialized organizations, such as Civil Society Organizations and Voluntary Agencies. The study also sourced materials from the reports of UN agencies working in Kenya, Voluntary Agencies and funding institutions. Some of the libraries and institutions that were of good help included university libraries, the United Nations Information Centre, British Institute of Eastern Africa, the British Council Library, Institute of African Studies and the internet. The neo-liberal approach as expounded by Kegley and Wittkopf (1997) and Keohane (1995) was adopted as its tool of analysis. The theory advocates that the state should accommodate an array of NGOs, transnational, supra-national and transgovernmental relation and coalition building in an effort to uplift the socio-economic status of the people. It was found out that religious organizations, voluntary agencies and Non-Governmental Organizations collaborate with the Government of Kenya in an attempt to uplift the socioeconomic status of the people of Turkana County.

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Figure 1: Map Showing Turkana County in Kenya
(Source: Google Maps, 2018.)

1. The Voluntary Movement Background

The religious pressure groups which agitated for the abolition of slavery at the end of the 18th century were closely associated with the movement which established the various missionary societies in Asia, Africa and Latin America. The initial preoccupation and the motivating factors of these missionary societies were the same: they were all filled with the commitment and the enthusiasm to look for the worlds newly discovered pagans, and to convert them to Christianity. Each missionary society tended to specialize in a particular region of the world and many took a part of Africa as their own special concern. The exploration by Europeans of the interior of Africa was

in large measure associated with the humanitarian ideas of the anti-slavery movement. It was as a missionary that Livingstone sought to develop his countrymen's enthusiasm for the advancement of Christianity and commerce which would relieve Africans from ignorance, famine and disease (Terra Viva, 1993).

Both the nature of their missionary services and their motivations were transported into their new situations, overseas. This correlates with the activities of Christian missionaries in the Dark Ages outside the dark bounds of the former Roman Empire led to the development of more civilized societies in Europe. Of course, this was not accomplished. It was the colonial powers which did, after their division of Africa. But they leaned heavily on the work of the missionaries, particularly in the educational and medical fields. In the post war period the colonial governments began to give attention to the problems of economic development, so too, the voluntary bodies began to extend their interests from the fields of education and health, to the problem of hunger and hence to the problems of economic development. But there were differences in approach reflected in the emergence of new forms International Voluntary Agencies (Young and Kent 2004:190).

The process of globalization in the 1980s and 1990s redefined the state and its role by limiting its sovereignty and depriving it of the functions of supervising market forces and co-ordination of social welfare. This resulted in the narrowing of the state's powers to that of protecting foreign investment and less to the protection of the citizen and the country (Momoh, 1999). The inherited colonial structures continued to serve the interests of the privileged dominant social strata by marginalizing the majority of the people from decision making that adversely affected their socio-economic and political life in Africa. The state became a centre of vested interests that developed into sharp contradictions and antagonisms. The immediate result was that the state was detached from the people, and the upsurge of instability entrenched it as an oppressive and parasitic institution. This was further worsened by its coercive structures. At the end of it all, the people of Africa no longer trusted it as an agent of social change and development (Chepkwony, 1987).

At the Ninth Session of the Economic Commission for Africa in 1969, a resolution was reached which *Inter alia* set to —promote the co-ordination of the work of the ECA, the specialized agencies of the UN and other international organizations with rural development programmes in Africa, in order to secure maximum impact of these programmes on the social and economic progress of the region (United Nations, 1970). In response to the resolution, a regional symposium was convened in August 1971, of representatives of twenty seven selected International Voluntary Agencies and of Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), International Labour Organization (ILO), World Health Organization (WHO), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), United Nations High Commission for Refugees (UNHCR), United Nations Children Education Fund (UNICEF), World Food Programme (WFP) and the Organization of African Unity (OAU) in order to consider and work out practical measures for fostering

and strengthening technical co-operation between ECA and the International Voluntary Agencies (ECOSOC, 1994).

Arising from the recommendations of the symposium, the ECA proceeded to establish a Voluntary Agencies Bureau (VAB), in September 1971, whose activities embraced the advisory and technical assistance to voluntary agencies on request in identification of suitable projects. Other activities included pre- investment studies and formulation of viable projects, field management of on-going projects and project evaluation exercises, publication of Comprehensive Directories of activities of voluntary agencies in member states, publicity for the work of voluntary agencies and Local Self-help Projects through a Development Education Programme by means of radio and other mass media, support for the Africa Co-operative Savings and Credit Association (ACOSCA) in mobilizing local savings for rural development, dissemination of new ideas on simple village technology, promotion of concentrated aid to countries with special needs of technical assistance and publication of a quarterly rural development newsletter on activities of the VAB on field experiences at project level .

Since 1972 when the Stockholm Declaration was pronounced, NGOs have played an enormous role in environmental issues in international society in a variety of ways. First, they created channels of communication that were later used by states representatives in order to conduct intergovernmental negotiations. Second, they informed national and international action on environment, drought, famine and food security. Third, they contributed to the scientific debate and therefore helped achieve common scientific understandings on technical aspects of environmental problems (Clarke and Timberlake, 1982).

The NGOs emerged in the late 20th century as important partners to both national governments and international agencies where they engaged each other in diplomacy, conflict resolution and reconstruction. Like international relief agencies, NGOs responded to major failures on the part of the international community to deal effectively with global problems. Too often, intergovernmental bodies and agencies proved too slow and cumbersome in dealing with emerging crisis situations. Also both international agencies and governments often have institutional and political limitations that hamper their effectiveness in situations of enormous complexity and delicacy. NGOs by contrast are often able to operate in very difficult circumstances.

A fundamental factor that pushed the policy towards targeting the aid dependent economies was the changing perception of aid and the centrality of poverty in policy discourse. In many African countries, aid played an important role in shaping socio-economic policy. At the same time, aid policies were embedded in the overall policies of donor countries. Not surprisingly, then any shifts in the ideological underpinnings of social and economic policies in the donor countries were bound to spill over to the principal of aid. Many donor countries accepted the major premises of adjustment. They more critically inclined to give a human face to the adjustment process by providing funds that would be aimed at mitigating poverty and despair in Africa (World Bank, 1990).

Such programmes were to be palliatives that would minimize the more glaring inequities that their policies had perpetuated. Funds were made available to ensure that a so called safety net of social services would be provided for the poor. The ever willing NGO sector was preferred. Another reason for the preference for targeting was that aid was understood not so much in terms of helping developing countries but in terms of helping the poor. It was believed that the NGOs would be more close to the poor than the state which was marred by corruption and misappropriation of aid funds by powerful individuals in African governments. In the context of donor fatigue it became politically necessary that aid directly reached the poor (Mkandawire, 2005). The state's failure therefore gave room to the proliferation of NGOs in Africa as an alternative engine to socio-economic change and development especially among the poor and unprivileged members of a given society. This therefore created an aspiration and desire to bring about lasting socio-economic change and to meet the basic needs of the common man which have either been too slow or not forthcoming within bilateral and multi-lateral state to state development co-operation (Khobotlo, 2001). The experience of famine relief efforts since 1974 in Africa by NGOs and the UN agencies made many African governments to be more willing to entrust the welfare of its people to the international development community. The situation was necessitated by the fact that like the colonial state, the post-colonial state was a repressive mechanism in charge of an export oriented economy that was designed to serve those in its management at the expense of the ordinary poor folk in the rural areas and other unprivileged groups (Nzongola, 1987).

NGOs were positively received by African states to assist in socio-economic development because of several reasons. According to Hyden (1980), NGO staff are normally highly motivated and altruistic in behaviour, they function economically due to their small size and their decentralized decision making process and structure; and lastly they are independent of the government and are therefore able to develop demands for public services and resources thereby facilitating the work of a government ministry in the rural areas.

The reasons for that were that the NGOs have legitimacy and operational access that do not raise concerns about sovereignty as governmental activities sometimes do. They facilitate and update extensive fact-finding missions, engage in dialogue with a wide range of groups, map out strategies for solving problems and galvanize action by national governments and international organizations to help stabilize crises. With their extensive field operations and their networks of local contacts, these groups have access to a wide array of information about the crisis that is not available to either international organizations or national governments. They had regular consultative meetings bringing together governments and NGOs to exchange information and offer critical advises and analyzed data about how the regional governments can help communities in marginalized areas (Princen and Finger, 1994).

There was increasing recognition more generally that NGOs amongst other providers, such as the church and the commercial sector can play a key role in the

delivery of health care where the state was unable to do this. Government donor contracting to such group's performance based agreement became increasingly popular. The NGOs collaborated with the government by exchanging information and advise by giving recommendations. These are the key elements of neo-liberal thought. The NGOs have a more positive view of pastoralists but may vary in their strategies. They may go in for restoring the pastoral systems, for instance after droughts. Such a strategy normally means various forms of restocking. Actually, NGOs circumvent public structures and deal with what they refer to —civil society. A particular element with NGOs is that they often come through relief operations, but remain on the scene as active socio-economic agencies (Khobotlo, 2001). Like other independent African states, Kenya was considered by citizens as the main provider of services, such as employment, education, healthcare, shelter, water projects, road construction and housing. The national resource allocation in the form of annual budget involved the financing of the above mentioned services in different parts of the country. Indeed Kenya was a welfare state (Republic of Kenya, 1969).

The implementation of the IMF and World Bank policies in Kenya exacerbated the decline of the state's role in welfare provision. The withholding of funding and loans by the development partners to Kenya compounded an already fragile socio-economic situation. This led to the opening of new avenues. For the first time Arid and Semi Arid Lands areas were opened to NGO agencies both local and international. They became the prime providers of social welfare in the region (Gimode, 2004:303). The government of Kenya through Sessional Paper No1 of 1992 on Development and Employment in Kenya accepted the recommendation that rigidity be avoided in the implementation of the Act on NGOs and there was to be continuous dialogue and effective collaboration between the government and NGOs. The government implemented the recommendations through the NGO Organizations Act of 1990 (Republic of Kenya, 1992).

2. The Voluntary, Faith and NGOs in Turkana County

The first NGOs to set foot in ASAL regions of Kenya aimed at providing relief to the communities hit by deteriorating economic and ecological conditions. The main agencies included Oxfam, World Vision, GTZ, Medicines Sans Frontiers, ICRC and Red Crescent and Action Aid (Gimode, 2004:303). It should be noted that these agencies were initially concerned with Somali and Ethiopian refugees. Their main aim was to provide medicines, relief food, clothes, temporary shelter, sinking of boreholes and maintenance of shallow wells. No sooner did they provide these services to refugees than they realized that the locals were equally deprived and needed even more attention than refugees. Consequently, the exposed inability of the state to cope with development challenges and disasters in the ASAL Districts left the state with no option but to allow NGOs to operate. The state embraced neo-liberal approach to socio-economic development, the theoretical tool of analysis of this study.

The NGOs played very critical roles in socio-economic development in Turkana County particularly in the provision of curative and preventive services, education, water, rehabilitation of socially distressed members of the community, disaster management, conflict resolution, afforestation, poverty alleviation, and youth programmes. All their programmes were well incorporated in the District Development Committee Programmes and therefore supplemented to a great extent to the government efforts in so many areas (Mukoo, O.I, 2007). The Government of Kenya through the Arid Lands Resource Management (a department in the Ministry of Special Programmes) in partnership with Oxfam GB in the years 2005/2006, managed to achieve the following; ten Trapezoidal bunds constructed in Kibish and 13 contours Bunds Constructed in Kalemungorok. All these were to assist the community in water harvesting. Despite all efforts and initiatives undertaken by the government, NGOs and CBOS, the impact gained needed to be sustained. The state through the National Aids Control Council (NACC) participated in channeling funds directly to the Community Based Organizations (CBOs) whose proposals were approved by it. The community members were aware of the existence of this fund though not many had been involved in its management.

Several NGOs including Oxfam and World Vision in partnership with the Ministry of Agriculture implemented food security initiatives in the district between the years 1998-2006. This stakeholder working necessitated the formation of an Agricultural Service Provider Consultative Forum (ASPF), which was a subcommittee of the District Steering Group (DGS) that coordinated the implementation of all agricultural activities. The Government of Kenya in collaboration with several Church Based Organizations (CBOs) in the years 2004-2005 funded several schools in the district. The government alone contributed Ksh.2.1 million to five schools namely Nakwamekwi Kataboi, AIC Kangitit Girls Secondary, St Mary's and Kalokol Mixed boarding school. All schools apart from Kataboi had completed their projects. To ease pressure on natural resources, alternative sources of livelihood were sought in conjunction with NGOs and other government of Kenya departments. The communities are now utilizing aloe vera and gum from the *Acacia seneangalease* which they sell to the Salt Lick Limited (Makau, O.I2007). The following are Non-Governmental Organizations, Voluntary Organizations, Civil Society Organizations and Faith Based Organizations that supplemented the Government of Kenya in socio-economic transformation of the people of Turkana County during the period under review.

2.1 The Catholic Diocese of Lodwar

The largest and strongest Faith Based Organization in Turkana County is the Diocese of Lodwar. The opening up of the district to other districts in the country was due to the efforts of the Catholic Church which has sunk numerous boreholes, built many primary schools and secondary schools including Lodwar High School which has since been handed over to the Government. It has put up many medical facilities which include

Kakuma Hospital which runs one of the most successful clinics and sponsors Child Based Health Care (CBHC) programme.

While the primary work of the Catholic Diocese of Lodwar is evangelization, the Diocese had various departments dealing with different aspects of human and institutional development. The Diocese was Co-terminus with the administrative district of Turkana and operated through the structure of its departments, committees and twenty three parishes (Melvin, 0.I,2007).The Diocese sponsored 177 Early Childhood's Development Centers (ECD), supported 95 primary schools and 32 Adult Education classes. It also runs the Saint Clare of Assisi Home Craft Centre for Girls in Kakuma had a number of members on the Lodwar Youth Polytechnic Board, supported Turkana Integrated School for the Blind in Katilu and was involved in informal education in a number of centers.

Diocese of Lodwar Health Programme provided curative and primary health care. It operated through 9 units including Kakuma Mission Hospital, 2 Health Centres in Loragun and Nakwamoru and 6 Primary Health Care programmes at Nadapal, Lowareng'ak, Lokori, Kanamkemer, Nakwamekwi and Nariokotome. These then run one dispensary and Seventeen satellite clinics. It also worked in partnership with the Terre des Hommes Medical Air Service and the Government of Kenya. The services offered included, Curative Health Care initiatives, maternal client activities, child health and nutrition activities, immunization activities, School Health Education on home visits; staff capacity building and HIV/AIDS care (Jertsen, 0, I, 2007). The programme dealt with Civic Education Awareness, Governance and Advocacy, Gender and legal education awareness.

3. Legal Education Awareness

Its programme objectives included: to enhance the capacity of all citizens to actively participate in every aspect of governance, to monitor the activities of all the local government performance with the aim of encouraging people to get actively involved in decision making about priority projects in the area, to empower people through information gathering analysis and dissemination to programme participation, to empower traditional structure and the provincial administration, to promote Human Resource Based Governance, to explore the possibility of introducing legal awareness and human rights education to schools, explore the possibility of facilitating civic education, to instill a sense of nationhood, common responsibility among the Turkana nomads, promote local, regional and national unity through peace initiatives, facilitate dialogue forums at all levels of governance, create a working relationship with other partners, CBOs and NGOs, to promote peace building efforts, enhance the capacity of human rights organizations to respond to current political transition, enhance effectiveness of work through building linkages with other human rights actors, monitor performance with a view of protecting, promoting and fulfilling universal accepted human rights standards, and promotion of gender equity (Melvin, 0.I,2007).

The other main purpose of the Diocese is to support the vulnerable in the community. These are the aged, the physically challenged, malnourished children, drought affected households, widows and orphaned children. The programmes undertaken included: the Ewoi Programme for the Aged, Nadirkonyen Street Children Centre, St Luke's Home for the Hearing Impaired, Nakwamekwi, and John Paul II Home for the Physically Handicapped in Lokichar and famine relief activities. It helped women in leadership and development trainings, HIV/AIDS awareness, entrepreneurship and income generating activities and practical skills. The youth empowerment programme activities included: the youth as agents of peace and reconciliation, leadership and formation, girl child advocacy, training of trainers, income generating activities and trainings, sports, music and drama festivals (Lodoket, O.I, 2007). In the years 2000 and 2006 the water department was able to have 10 rock dams, 1 sand pan, 4 boreholes, 24 shallow wells, 1 spring protection, 4 Augur rigs manufacture, 6 water tanks installed, 13 constitutions formed, 14 workshops and pump maintenance unit of community water points throughout the district (Melvin, O.I,2007.)

3.1 Merlin

Merlin is a British humanitarian NGO, providing health care to population in crises. It exists to provide an immediate and effective response to medical emergencies throughout the world. The assistance provided by Merlin is targeted at the most vulnerable populations who have the greatest health needs and poorest access to healthcare provision. Merlin focuses on providing quality healthcare to population regardless of race, religion and political affiliation, to support people affected by war or natural disaster anywhere in the world. Merlin programmes were guided by the operational needs of the particular situation on the ground. It provides the quality healthcare addressing needs within the realms of infectious disease control, primary and secondary health care and maternal and child healthcare. It works with the Government of Kenya in the existing local health structures and collaborates with other agencies where possible to increase efficiency and effectiveness of humanitarian assistance. The interventions coverage areas were Kolokol, Kerio, Lokitang, Lapur, Central, Kaaleng, Loima, Lokichar, and Turkwel Divisions. These areas were practiced according to the results of the surveys undertaken in collaboration with Oxfam (Mukoo, O.I, 2007).

3.2 Riam – Riam Turkana

Riam Riam is a local organization started in 2001 as a Peace and Development Committee in the district. It is an umbrella body consisting of local CBOs dealing with peace and conflict resolution within and without Turkana. Its core functions included the building of capacities of pastoralists, their leaders, local organizations, to influence decision making process, support democratic governance, influence policy processes and facilitate formation of local voices especially those of women, support and promote innovative conflict resolution and peace building initiatives, mitigate the spread and

effects of HIV/AIDS pandemic and support other socio-economic activities that will improve and secure livelihoods of the poor communities and groups in the district (Lomodei O.I, 2007).

Table 1: Riam Riam Funding 2005/2006

Donor	Amount Ksh
Dodoch Turkana conflict Mitigation Programme – USAID	4.0 M
Oxfam – GB Turkana Annual Budget	1.50 M
Practical Action (ITDG)	200,000
Arid Lands Resource Management Project II	1.30 M
VSF – B Support in part	_____
LWF – Support in part	_____

Source: Ram Riam Turkana

The organization operates district wide with special attention to conflict prone corridors that include Todonyang, Kibish, Lokichogio, Oropoi, Lokirama, Lorengippi, Kinuk and Kapedo. Its main achievement include the reduction of tension between the Turkana and their neighbours as well as improved relation between them in that Merille children can now study in Turkana. (Asabit, O.I, 2007). However, efforts to deal with peace around the Turkana – Pokot corridor were the most challenging. This is mainly due to relatively unsuccessful government interventions to exhaustively provide security in the area. At the same time, the local leadership in the two communities are yet to embrace virtues of peaceful co-existence of communities. Its strategy collaborators include the Ethiopian Pastoralist Research and Development Association (EPARDA), Karamoja Kotido Peace initiative (KOPEIN), Moroto, Matheniko Development Forum (MADEFO), Karamoja – AgroPastoralist Development Organization and West Pokot Development Committee.

3.3 Christian Children’s Fund – Kenya (CCF) Turkana Cluster

Christian Children’s Fund (CCF) is an international non-profit making, non- secretariat, human development agency whose main aim is the improvement of the quality of life of disadvantaged children and their families. The organization started its operations in Kenya in the 1960s in response to children’s suffering brought about by the political, economic and social realities. (Williams, O.I, 2007). In Turkana District CCF operations started in consultation with the government around 1978 and by 2006, its development activities were carried out through the facilitated Community Based

Organizations working in Kitilu, Turkwel, Loima and parts of Central Lapur and Lokitang Divisions. The programme supported over two thousand enrolled children and impacts on additional over 140,000 other beneficiaries in these areas of coverage. The inventions carried out were in the core programme areas of education, health/nutrition and food security initiatives Its achievements include; increased pre-school and primary school enrolments, increased girl’s enrolment and performance for example in Lorugum Primary rose from 50 to 210 boarders and education to girls and

parents which helped to solve the problem of serious absenteeism from class by girls, improved learning environment demonstrated by more stimulating and attractive classrooms and stronger community support, 183 students in both secondary and tertiary levels of education benefited from part payment of school fees in 2005, supported the provision of supplementary food (wet feeding) to over 11,000 children in Early Childhood Development Centers for 10 months, which helped to reduce malnutrition rate from average of 35 percent to 23 per cent during 2004 – 2006 drought. Nadapal community used their allocation as food for work to create conventional canals irrigation.

3.4 Share International

Share International is a Faith Based Organization with activities that are geared towards community development. It works closely with the Turkana District Development Committee. Its annual funding amounts to five million shillings. The organization sponsors needy children from poor families in secondary and primary schools. From the year 2003, the organization was able to drill one borehole at Chok Chok, Napadal and Nayuu respectively. It also sponsors adult learning centers, constructed four classes in Napadal, Kantese, Loturerei and Naibun. It also pays teacher's salaries. The organization is training women on health education, soap making, small business and provision of nutritional supplements every month to targeted areas (Weehace, 0, I, 2007).

3.5 Oxfam

Since 1970s, Oxfam has undertaken some development activities in Turkana District in collaboration with various government ministries .In Kakuma the organization deals with livestock activities by providing medicine to livestock owners and arranging for some seminars about the care and treatment of animals and the use of vaccines. Oxfam in collaboration with World Vision are the major consignees for the famine relief food from WFP. These two agencies are responsible for receiving the food for distribution to sites in Kakuma, Lokichogio, Lokitaung, Kabish, Lokori and Katilu Divisions. The northern Divisions are the responsibility of Oxfam while the southern Divisions are being handled by World Vision (Eleman, 0, I, 2007).In 1996 it distributed relief food at Kalokol Division which had a positive impact to the people's welfare. It also initiated the security peace talks with Oxfam Kaabong in Uganda with the assistance of the provincial administration. In 1995, both the general and supplementary rations were being distributed between Oxfam and World Vision. Good co-ordination of the interventions existed between the concerned NGOs. The organization actively support and helps improve co-ordination initiatives at global and field level, which resulted in enhanced aid effectiveness. This includes UN led health clusters and other inter- agency coordination and donor groups. It also worked with other partners to enhance its operational capacity and increasingly worked with a wider range of state and non-state providers in Turkana District

3.6 AMREF

AMREF works in consultation with the Ministry of Health. The organization's projects and programmes include Hydatit Research and Control Programme and the provision of Primary Health Care (PHC) Community Based Health Care (CBHC) that offers basic health care, preventive and promotive services which include hydatit disease, malaria, typhoid and diarrhoea, sanitation education, provision of safe water and other related community based health activities. Its achievements included the construction of three dispensaries offering curative services and 10 – 15 days mobile health services provided per month for over 500 nomadic community members per month, established in 2003 latrine coverage among settled community at 17 per cent at the households. 18 households with an average households being 7, 126 community members are using pit latrines in Lopiding among more than 500 households. Disease incidence in humans in the district reduced from 7% (1983) to 5% (1993) to 3% (2004) and the desired behavior change in the community in destroying all Hydatit cysts from slaughtered animals and denying dogs having access to them is taking root but will take time till the community will actively control the disease by themselves (Waswa, O.I, 2007).

3.7 International Rescue Committee (IRC)

IRC serves refugees and communities victimized by oppression and violent conflict in the district and worldwide. This commitment is expressed in emergency relief, protection of human rights, post conflict development, resettlement assistance and advocacy. Its principles include the protection and promotion of human rights participation, capacity building, partnership and holistic programming. During the period 2005 – 2006 alone, the organization in collaboration with the government was able to construct Kadokorinyang gravity water points at Namadak, Kalobeyei, Oropoi, Kaleng and Lokichar, water tinkering at water stressed areas, water quality monitoring, provision of storage facilities i.e. plastic tanks to schools and communities and assessment of hygienic practices at Kaleng, Lokitaung, Turkwel, Kalokol, Kakuma and Kerio Divisions. In the year 2006 the organization received a funding amounting to Ksh 26,164,740 (Mohammed, O, I,2007).

3.8 The Red Cross

The Red Cross is an international NGO which participates in emergency services across the world. The organization participates in development and humanitarian activities as well. In Turkana District, the Red Cross Hospital at Lokichogio serves the emergency cases caused by the internal war conflict in the Sudan. In most cases, the hospital does not admit the locals with any kind of natural sickness and even those injured by raiders. The organization participates in recruiting and training of first aid instructors and trainers. It delivers lectures on first aid to Secondary Schools, Primary Schools, the Armed Forces and Civil Servants (Kiarie, O,I, 2007).

3.9 Kenya Red Cross Society

The organization is a key response agency in the country, and has a strong profile as a relief organization reaching out in all disasters. The society enjoys a lot of support from the Government of Kenya, the public and the media. The core objective of the organization is to alleviate human suffering and or save lives (Ewoi, O.I, 2007). Drought in Turkana District created an emergency situation that caused severe stress on the population in the affected areas. The lack of rains since 2004 resulted in critical water shortage, food insecurity, collapse of livestock market with dying livestock and famine. An overall assessment carried out in December 2005 by the organization led to the appeal issued to the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent to act. In that case, an emergency programme was initiated in March 2006 to tackle issues related to provision of water in the district. The achievements included the rehabilitation and installation of new generating sets and submersible pumps at Kibish Namadak, Nadapal and Oropoi boreholes. The organization also supplied 10 schools with 10,000 litres of P.V.C tanks and four tanks of 24,000 litres to four boreholes that the organization was rehabilitating.

3.10 Farm Africa

This organization undertakes camel improvement in the district. The project involves training on range management, health, social organization and small financial assistance to women groups. The agency builds structures, operates them and later transfers the same to the local community.

3.11 Food for the Hungry International (FHI)

The organization is involved in the provision of water to the communities. The water projects are later handed over to the communities who form water user's associations to sustain them. They are also involved in desalting of pans. It provided tools to the water user associations to undertake the desalting. The organization also closely with the Ministry of Education in the district promote education through sponsorship of children and schools development (Esore, O, I, 2007).

3.12 Harambee Movements

A large percentage of development projects and programmes intended to uplift the living standards of the people in the district were done by self-help movements named *Harambee*. One example of the success cases of *Harambee* movements included the establishment of Kangetit Girls Secondary School. A total of 1.5 Million shillings was collected for the construction of the dormitory and other educational facilities in 1975. The money was mostly donated by civil servants, teachers and businessmen working in the district. The other *Harambee* activities that were witnessed in the district in the late 1970s included those for the District *Harambee* Show and the fund to help the Turkana Children from poor families pay their school fees (Naibiswa, O.I, 2007).

3.13 Womankind

The organization assists the Ministry of Education in the provision of education through early childhood development, girl child development, and training on tailoring. It also participated in reproductive health training and income generating activities (Kirye, O.I, 2007).

3.14 GTZ

The organization is involved in livestock development, social services, water, health and education. It is also involved in the rehabilitation of boreholes. The Department of Agriculture and Livestock Development benefited through purchase of various implements training and construction. It supports nutrition programmes, buying of additional equipment for the mobile health units like tents and support of charitable organizations or programmes (Komen, O,I, 2007)

3.15 The Salvation Army

The church runs a number of nursery and secondary schools in the district. An example is the Lokitaung Secondary School.

3.16 Women Groups/ Women in Development

Women in Turkana District organized themselves in groups. By 1974, there were about seventy one women groups in the whole of Turkana District. One such groups included the Nawaitorong Women Group which was running a canteen, guest house and conference hall in Lodwar. Others are the Natole Women Group from Kalokol which was engaged in basketry and AIC Lodwar Women Group which also engaged in basketry and handcraft (Etabo O,I, 2007.)

3.17 African Inland Church

The A.I.C church started in 1979 the Morolem Irrigation Scheme in South Turkana which covered 62 hectares of basin irrigation with 985 plot holders. Water was absorbed from the Kerio River by means of gravity intake and 3 km of feeder canal. By double rooting sorghum, a good yield of between 5 and 12 ton/ha was achieved from the first crop in 1982 on the 25 ha then developed (Ikimat O,I, 2007).The mission worked hard to transform the socio-economic welfare of the Turkana people. It sponsored a number of schools and paying of school fees for needy children. The mission established a dispensary at Lokori but with some problems like shortage of staff and medicine. The mission also organized fishermen in Lake Turkana and managed to export 18,401 Kgs of dried fish between April 1977 and January 1978. By 2006, the church was sponsoring several schools and dispensaries in the County.

3.18 VSF – Belgium

Its mission is to improve the wellbeing of vulnerable populations in developing countries by improving animal health and production. Thus, VSF Belgium works with

livestock dependent communities whose livelihoods are threatened by shocks and vulnerability as a result of environmental, political and socio-economic circumstances. The organizational engagement with local communities has the dual role of targeting the provision of basic services to address immediate needs while building the capacity of its development partners to engage on long term development from within. The organization works to achieve these aims through strategic approaches combining both emergency and sustainable development initiatives in which emergency interventions are undertaken only when the context allows quick transition to sustainable development (Tavasi, 0,I,2007)

The main target population groups by VSF Belgium include the nomadic pastoralists' sedentary rural agro-pastoralists and urban and peri-urban agro-pastoralists. The organization operates in the central and south regions of Turkana District (including neighboring pastoralists' communities who interact with Turkana within the Karamoja Cluster. Its main sectors and activities included the improvement of animal productivity through community based approaches, improvement of water supply for livestock through construction of sub-surface dams and other water retention structures, improvement of economic returns through promotion of livestock marketing opportunities, supporting peace building and conflict resolution initiatives in the Karamoja Cluster region in collaboration with other partners and cross cutting issues – HIV/AIDS prevention, gender mainstreaming and development. The organization sources funds from the Belgian Government through – Belgian Survival Funds BSF – 75 percent, European Union – 15 percent and VSF Belgian own funds 10 percent.

3.19 Practical Action

Practical Action aims to eradicate poverty in developing countries through the development use of technology by demonstrating results, sharing knowledge and influencing others. The organization in consultation with the Government of Kenya promotes the market for products from pastoralists and agro pastoralists. In Turkana, the organization conducted training of farmers on Aloe Vera propagation, nursery establishment, harvesting, processing, marketing and market information, packaging and products development. Two women groups of Kalemngorok and Namoruputh successfully produced and sold aloe medicated soap, lotion and shampoo. Market promotion of Aloe products was officially launched by the Trade and Industry Minister in Lodwar town on 28th August 2006 and in Kakuma town on 29th August 2006 (Aseno, O.I, 2007). The organization also participated in peace building, to reduce the risks of conflicts over natural resources and support of internally displaced families in post conflicts areas, to maintain, develop or rebuild their livelihoods. The activities carried out included the formation in collaboration with Riam Riam Turkana of a peace committee, use of school communities as entry point to spreading messages of conflict mitigation and peace building as well as HIV/AIDS, Secondary Schools Drama Festivals, training on conflict management and revolving loan grants to small stock

projects. Some of the beneficiaries included the Namoruputh Self Help Group, Kshs.84, 000 and Ngiturkana Network Kshs.400, 000.

Furthermore, the organization was able to work with the state and other NGOs in areas of conflict resolution in the County. The NGOs that the organization worked together included Oxfam, Turkana Women Development Organization (TWDO) and World Vision. The achievements were as follows: No incidences of insecurity in Todonyang corridor. There is free movement of the Merille in the County and Merrile children are now enrolled in Kenyan primary schools for example Loarengak Primary School. War mongering among the Nyangatom has been managed. The hitherto volatile areas around Todonyang have calmed and Merrile and the Turkana are grazing freely. Tension between the Turkana and Toposa at Lokichogio has been reduced and well managed, almost thirty percent of pastoralists around the area are Toposa of Sudan. Fishing in Lake Turkana is flourishing with no incidences safe for first week of August 2006 where two nets belonging to Turkanas were stolen but the Peace Committee followed and returned them. Incidences of insecurity have been minimized at Oropoi mainly across border conflicts. Incidences of livestock theft at Loima is being handled. Negotiated return of human population abducted during raids was successful (Kadir, Nawoi, Ethuro, O.I, 2007).

3.20 National Chamber of Commerce and Industry

The organization works to enable small enterprises to flourish, create self-reliance, promote self-employment, create employment opportunities and promotion of business in the district covering all frontiers. The organization sources funds from members' contributions. Some of the challenges encountered by the organization include: poor road infrastructure, all goods especially food stuff are bought in Kitale, lack of business investors in the district as traders prefer to invest outside Turkana and traders who acquired loans do not repay them on time for others to benefit (Abong'ai O.I,2007).

3.21 Kenya Freedom from Hunger Council

The Kenya Freedom from Hunger Council for National Development became involved in the relief effort in Turkana District in 1993. The organization has been tirelessly participating in funding and offering technical assistance to farming, Self Help Groups and raising funds to the families of famine stricken people in Turkana District in cases of emergency. It raises funds through the Kenya Freedom from Hunger Walk conducted every year in major towns with support from the government and the public (Weehace, O.I., 2007).

3.22 World Vision

World Vision as an NGO is involved in vaccination campaigns in the entire district in liaison with the Ministry of Livestock Development. It also donates drugs and equipment for health centers in the district. The organization also sponsors children to receive minimum education package, such as school uniform, subsidiary of medical

treatment bills, exercise books and pens. It also embarks on food security campaigns, for instance the development of Napeikar irrigation scheme and canal worth Kshs.1.5Million. Other activities include the sinking of shallow wells along the River Turkwel, supporting medical facilities for instance in Kalokol A.I.C Dispensary and Kangatotha Dispensary for the supply of drugs, construction of classes for example at Napeikar, Kakwanyang and Kangatotha Primary Schools, training of teachers, training of school management committees, lending of loans for business for example in 2005 about 10 million shillings were disbursed to community members carrying out business in Lodwar, Kalokol, Kainuk, Lokichar and Kakuma (Opiyo, O.I., 2007).

4. Issues Raised Against NGOs

NGOs are perceived as alternative to the state for socio-economic development and change. However, NGOs and civil associations should be examined not in a uni-linear or unidirectional manner, but should rather be seen as multi formations with their own complexities and contradictions in spite of what their own claims are (Chepkwony, 1987). This is because they are both vector and fetter or catalyst and constraint. NGOs are flourishing in Africa not because the state has failed, but because the majority of the population was disempowered. The arguments brought to the fore are that NGOs serve two purposes; firstly, the delegitimization of the state and secondly turning Africans into guinea pigs for experimentation.

A deeper insight reveal that some NGOs are run and operated by one person and at the same time bigger NGOs kill the smaller ones by intimidating or using their contact with the funding circle to deny such small NGOs funding. Another fact is that many NGOs are more concerned about what space they can appropriate for themselves than about creating the enabling condition that will emancipate the people. Hence, in certain instances both NGOs and the state have become obstacles towards opening up democratic social and economic spaces. Some NGOs started off as specialized NGOs and then became generalists so that they can get funding from all quarters and worse is their faking of evaluation reports to representatives of donor agencies (Chepkwony, 1987, Khobotlo, 2001).

NGOs especially those from Western Countries receive a lot of financial subsidies from their governments. These governments give criteria which the NGO must adhere to. The contention arises when the criteria and defined priorities of the Western governments negate the original aims of NGOs. Consequently, the independence of NGOs is compromised. The rules set by these governments at the end give demand for technocrats who take over from volunteers and this directly compromise the motivation of the staff (Chepkwony, 1987:358-360).

A problem emerged where NGOs or Civil Societies lobbied hard to ensure that states are put aloof in development matters in their areas of operation. Some NGOs do not want to be audited or their activities assessed (Khobotlo, 2001). It will be wise if these organizations work closely with governments of states concerned. The reason

being that sound policies and strategies enable a country to effectively plan for the future on a long term basis. This in turn makes it easy for foreign technical assistance or any other form of foreign assistance to be channeled into predetermined national goals and objectives (Khubotlo, 2001). If this is not checked a country's development can be piecemeal and disjointed driven by uncoordinated foreign donor sponsored projects and sporadic investments.

In the early and mid-1990s there emerged numerous international NGOs who worked without the requisite coordination. Lack of coordination breeds duplication and inability to sustain development projects after those who started have gone back to their home countries (Mosse, 2004). The cases of duplication and stalling of NGO projects in Turkana County are very common (Makau, O.I., 2007). It is ironical that as the UN and NGOs struggle hard to strengthen their working relationship, some critical issues emerged, for instance a lack of mutual trust and in some cases, lack of respect still remained.

Some NGOs used every forum to criticize the UN system, particularly on issues regarding the body's peacekeeping efforts and the activities of the World Bank (United Nations, 1993:57). Some UN agencies have also been skeptical on the activities of NGOs and their ineffectiveness. In the *Human Development Report 1993*, issued by the UNDP for instance, the agency wondered whether NGOs have had as much success in tackling poverty as they claim "*Nobody really knows ... what seems clear is that even people helped by successful (NGO) projects still remain poor*" (United Nations, 1993). The report furthermore argued that NGOs reached less than 20% of the 1.3 billion people living in absolute poverty and urged them to engage more with governments to avoid being marginalized in national debates on development. NGOs especially those operating in Turkana County to a large extent do not involve the local people in planning and implementation of their projects. Some of them do not even provide employment to the locals and if they do, they are given low cadre jobs citing lack of qualification. Even O Level leavers from outside the County were employed at the expense of equally qualified residents. In short, some NGOs practice tribalism and nepotism in employment (Lopuwa, Ethuro, Lokidor, O.I., 2007).

5. Conclusion

The state's failure to meet the independence expectations of the people and especially the poor gave room to the proliferation of NGOs. These NGOs and other development partners were positively received to assist in speeding up socioeconomic development among the poor and unprivileged members of the society. Turkana being an ASAL County and majority of its residents being poor pastoralists, NGOs were called in to assist. The NGOs contributed a great deal in uplifting the socioeconomic development of the people of Turkana District. These organizations in collaboration with the state managed to improve security situation among the Turkana and their neighbours, improved education, healthcare, social welfare provisions that targeted the vulnerable

members of the community that include the elderly, children, drought affected households, widows orphans and the handicapped. Other areas in which the multi-sectoral approach benefited the people of Turkana District included the empowerment of women through education, education of women on leadership, income generating activities, youth empowerment, HIV/AIDS Programmes and provisions of water, livestock development and agriculture development through irrigation. The NGOs did not survive criticism either. Some of the issues raised against NGOs included the unclear picture created in that eyebrows were raised as to whether truly the NGOs were contributing enough to poverty eradication, accountability on the NGO activities was lacking and foreign NGOs trying to dictate and control what should be done in Africa through their governments. This was seen as a way of advancing the Western ideologies and interests through NGO or simply neo-colonialism. Other factors included duplication of activities by these NGOs, lack of sustainability, disjointed or uncoordinated projects, stalling of projects and non-involvement of the local people in their planning and implementation of projects.

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Appendix: The List of Respondents

Name	Sex	Occupation	D.O.I
Abong' ai Isiah	M	Businessman, Lodwar	30.7.07
Ahmed Ali. Y.	M	Businessman, Lokichogio	7.7.07
Alfred Waswa	M	Employee, AMREF	27.7.7
Aregai John	M	Political activist	30.8.07
Aseno Ochieng	M	Coordinator, Practical Action	27.7.07
Atabo Jane	F	Chair, Nawaitorong Women Group	31.8.07
Baliach Hillary	M	Employee, Merlin	11.5.07
Ekidor Michael	M	Youth Leader, Katilu Y.G.	31.8.08
Etabo Lolio	M	Youth Leader, Rudolf Y.G	23.7.07
Ethuro Esokoi	M	Businessman	12.5.07
Ewoi John	M	Coordinator KRCS, Turkana	24.7.07
Ikeno Sylvester	M	Teacher	10.5.07
Ikimat M.A.	F	AIC Mission, Lodwar	30.8.07
Jertsen Elin	F	Nurse, Kakuma Mission Hospital	28.7.07
Kadir Suleiman	M	Civil Servant, M.O.P.W	24.7.07
Kirye Jane	F	Employee, Womankind	10.5.07
Komen Jonathan	M	Employee, GTZ	30.8.07
Lodoket Lomear	M	Social worker, Turkana	26.7.07
Lokidor Peter	M	Student, Moi University	12.5.07
Lomodei Susan	F	Member Riam Riam	24.7.07
Lopuwa William Lokoru	M	Turkana elder	28.7.07
Maina Joyce Wangare	F	Volunteer, Oxfam	6.7.07
Makau Justus	M	DDO, Turkana	11.5.07
Melvin Timothy	M	Priest	23.7.07
Mukoo Benedict	M	Coordinator, Merlin	10.5.07
Nabiswa Irine	F	Civil Servant (MoC), Lodwar	23.7.07
Nwoi Elizabeth	F	Teacher, Oropoi Primary	24.7.07
Odhiambo Okoth Samwel	M	Civil Servant (MoT) Turkana	10.5.07
Opiyo James, O.	M	Volunteer World Vision, Turkana	26.7.07
Peter Eregai	M	Turkana elder	27.7.07
Tavasi F. W.	M	Deputy coordinator, VSF Belgium	30.8.07
Wambani Esther	F	Volunteer, World Vision	28.7.07
Weehace V. W.	F	Missionary, Share International	30.8.07
Williams Clayton	F	Employee CCF, Turkana	27.7.07

Philip Kipkemboi Chemelil
THE CONTRIBUTION OF VOLUNTARY, FAITH BASED AND NON GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS
TO SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN TURKANA COUNTY, KENYA 1986-2006

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